

DIAGNOSTICS OF PROFESSIONAL READINESS OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS FROM A LOGICAL POINT OF VIEW

Fakhriddinov Yokubjon

Gulistan state pedagogical institute

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Abstract. *In this article, the general qualification requirements for the main types of professional activities of the graduates of the pedagogic education field cover the editorial, scientific-research, spiritual-educational, organizational-management activities. The improvement of mechanisms for diagnosing the level of teacher training was analyzed.*

Keywords: *diagnostics, tool, task, pedagogical activity, professional activity.*

Introduction: Today, the issue of improving the education system, training highly qualified and competitive personnel is defined as one of the most important tasks of the education policy of our country. The fact that the educational process in our country is placed on a national-spiritual basis is clearly defined in our Constitution. In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 “On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” No. PD-4947 in the direction “Development of the social sphere” “...improving the quality of general secondary, secondary special and higher education and implementing measures for their development”. Ensuring the implementation of tasks defined in other regulatory and legal documents aimed at the development of this field, such as the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 2015 “On approval of state educational standards of higher education”, continuous development The formation of a creative, socio-politically active, spiritually rich person in the education system and the training of highly qualified competitive personnel create the necessary conditions. [1,2,3].

Pedagogical diagnostics “has always been an independent direction in terms of its goals, tasks, and field of application. However, until today, there are scientists who believe that pedagogical diagnostics is an abstract and controversial direction, that it can be accepted only as a program. Therefore, today there are several interpretations of the term “pedagogical diagnosis”, which are diverse and complex in terms of content.

Analysis of literatures on the topic: According to K.Leongard, G.Royleke, R.Rollet, A.E.Lishko, A.Bass, A.Shmelev, editorial diagnosis is the process of obtaining information necessary for optimization and facilitation of editorial activity.[4]

H.Feger, N.Retillon, V.Bogatskyi put forward the opinion that pedagogical diagnosis is separated from it as a certain part of psychological diagnosis. A.Kerns’ and Ya.Yirasek’s orientation tests for determining the tendency of young people to learn, D.B. Elkonin's “Graphic dictation, A.L. Wenger’s “Dot painting”, L.Shvansar’s “Mental development diagnosis”, V.V. Kholmovskaya's “Children at school age such methods as “diagnosing students’ abilities” are popular [5]. The “Uniform Plan for the Development of Education” of Germany, which occupies a leading position in the field of education, states: “The concept of pedagogical diagnosis, the coverage of all processes and problems in the field of pedagogical practice, the measurement of mastery and the effectiveness of the educational process, education refers to the options for determining the opportunities of each person in the field of education, especially the options for choosing the desired profession and level of education in the school education system” [6]. It is

important that the main focus here is on helping to choose a profession. The German scientist Mauerman writes: “Educational diagnostics establishes a connection between mastering and preparation for the educational process, correctly defines the educational goal of the educational process, and assesses the appropriateness of educational and organizational forms to the conditions”. K. Klauer criticized a number of scientists who defined pedagogical diagnostics and said, “It is difficult for pedagogical diagnostics (diagnostics) to perform the tasks of classification (categorization) at the same time, therefore it should not define the essence of the term pedagogical diagnostics”. Pedagogical diagnosis consists of a set of attempts to make actual editorial decisions and judgments. Russian scientist N.G. Zvereva puts forward the idea that “pedagogical diagnosis is a process of identifying various educational situations, learning, and knowing the level of various abilities of the participants of the educational system” [7]. Russian scientist N.N. Obozova, M.M. Dudina writes: “Editorial diagnosis is a set of activities that determine the individual and professional qualities of an editor in the diagnosis of the educational process, help in the creative development of an individual, and increase the success of the editorial team” [8].

Moreno Montessori believes that “pedagogical diagnosis is used to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, enrich its content, and certify it.” Also, D.I. Nesterenko, L. Bilousova, Ingenkamr, I.R. Rodlasi, N.V. Zolotikh, K.S. Scientists such as Orlova gave different definitions and comments to pedagogical diagnosis in their research.

According to the definition of the educational scientist O.V. Almazova, educational diagnosis is a field of science between the disciplines of educational science and psychology, which studies the personality of the child, his individual characteristics, development dynamics and factors affecting them.

Pedagogical diagnosis is aimed at the comprehensive development of a person’s skills and abilities, and the formation of their personality. Physiologist V.M. Polonsky researched the possibilities of correctly understanding the personality of a child and analyzing his actions. The great statements of the East, Ibn Sina, Farabi and Beruni, noted in their scientific works about the existence of unique human potential and the need to always pay serious attention to it. Students should be able to enter the “unique world” of the child in the educational and educational process and organize it on the basis of pedagogical-psychological diagnostic methods suitable for his age characteristics.

In her research, F.B. Valikhojayeva said that pedagogical diagnosis is a science of pedagogical diagnosis, in which diagnosis consists of conclusions about the state and characteristics of the subject based on joint analysis of descriptions. According to S.V. Safonova, O.A. Fadeeva, E.E. Leonova, it is very important to identify the object of pedagogical diagnosis as a person who develops together with the external conditions surrounding him:

1. To consider the results of pedagogical activity in an integral connection with pedagogical conditions that can determine one or another result.
2. To have a scientifically based point of view about the relationship between the components of the pedagogical process leading to the external pedagogical reality and the developmental results they determine.
3. Carefully interpret the obtained results, always taking into account the interests and rights of the person acting as a research object.

D.A. Choriyeva, V.V. Grishin, G.N. Ibragimova in the manual “Methods of psychodiagnostics in the educational process” published by D.A. Choriyeva, V.V. Grishin, is a

developing person. The object of socio-pedagogical diagnosis is considered its main and important component. "Entering the social-pedagogical diagnostic object means the answer to the question about the diagnostic object, that is, the social-pedagogical diagnosis is the definition of the pedagogical space where the diagnostic search is carried out." Judging from the definitions of pedagogical diagnostic functions, such a gap is the pedagogical process. According to L.M. Volobuyeva, the definition and substantiation of the editorial diagnosis is determined by the type of educational institution, the curriculum and the organization of the editorial process based on this information. The group of students performing diagnostics implements a comprehensive approach to the study of a child with developmental disorders. Based on the diagnosis, the decision is made collectively. The work of the diagnostic team is based on a certain system, taking into account the individual characteristics of the child.

In his works, K. Zaripov stated that the main goal of educational and psychological diagnostics is to provide diagnostic and correctional, psychological, medical and educational assistance to children with developmental disorders in educational institutions, to provide them with adequate conditions for education and upbringing. stated that it consists of creating [9].

Summarizing all the definitions given above, we consider it permissible to express the following opinion. If we consider "pedagogical diagnosis - the process of analyzing, guaranteeing and making recommendations of the results of the editorial system of the person of the editor and those who interact with him", then the mechanisms for diagnosing the readiness of future specialists in their professional activities are "the preparation of future specialists for their professional activities" It covers the process of diagnostics, its scope, laws, principles, methods, forms, criteria, the content and essence of systematization and improvement of technologies, guaranteeing and giving recommendations.

Yo.Nurimbekova stated that the research of educational and educational process, its methods differ from scientific-pedagogical research methods in that it envisages the application of actual educational measures to a particular student or group of children and youth.

G.N.Ibragimova, D.A.Choriyevalar social pedagogical - psychological diagnosis - this direction includes sociology, social pedagogy, pedagogy in its work, and includes individuals, editors, groups of parents, radio, television, newspapers, etc. put forward the proposal that it is directed to study the influence of mass communication means, the rights and obligations of individuals, and the relationship between them. Pedagogical diagnosis, which serves to improve the educational process, is considered an integral part of every planned educational process, it constantly monitors how the students learn the educational material, and tries to find solutions to the problems in the educational process. An experienced and skilled editor understands the difficulties that arise in the educational process better than others.

In the process of pedagogical diagnostic activity, students should organize it correctly in order to carry out the activity in accordance with the purpose. But in blind situations, students' cognitive activities are limited. Students choose fields based on their personal interest in learning through play, study, and work, which are the main types of children's activities. The main type of activity - communication is effectively used. According to a group of scientists such as N.A. Gaibova, S.Kh. Jalilova, N.A. Kayumova, G.Kozlova [10], activity can be active and passive. A child's activity can become more active or decrease under the influence of environment and education. In the development of a person's personality, his ability to love with his whole body, to show his potential, to work, to show himself as a person shows a sense of satisfaction with his

work. As a result, his active participation in social work is evident. Active learning in the process of learning leads to deep and solid acquisition of knowledge, to demonstrate one's abilities. Activity to knowledge ensures the intellectual development of the student.

Research methodology. In the course of their activities, editors should take into account the individual characteristics of each student, take into account the basic principles of education and training and all their requirements. This requires that the educational process in higher education institutions be organized in a logical sequence on the basis of special educational and methodological programs. An incorrect diagnosis not only invalidates all the efforts of the specialist, but also destroys the possibility of eliminating the existing problem and may cause the emergence of another, more serious problem. Eliminating the negative factors identified on the basis of editorial diagnostics is also important in the process of educational correction. Educational diagnostics: first of all, it facilitates the process of individual education; and from this, it greatly helps to choose a specific educational direction and specialty. It helps to determine how the future pedagogy in the system of higher education acquires a specialty. With the help of editorial diagnostics, the process of acquiring professional knowledge and skills in practical, seminar, laboratory training is analyzed and the results of education, that is, professional training, are determined. In this, it is necessary not only to summarize the results of education and professional training, but also to consider the dynamics of their change. The main goal of pedagogical diagnostics in a higher education institution is to prepare students for the profession in the future, to teach them to be independent, to be able to behave properly in the social environment, in activities, and to help them plan their activities in the near future. formation of the need to strive for excellence, and, if necessary, to identify factors that negatively affect or may affect the process of education and the development of the necessary social and professional qualities of students.

Conclusions and suggestions. An innovative approach to education is understood as the technologicalization of the process of teaching and educating students, that is, how to organize each step of education, the goal, the obtained result, the professional knowledge, skills and qualifications formed in students, and the achievement of the goal.

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